

Paper 15

**A STUDY ON THE STATUS OF INTELLIGENCE AND REASONING
ABILITY OF NINTH STANDARD STUDENTS**

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ABSTRACT

Intelligence and reasoning ability involve the ability to think, solve problems, analyse situations and comprehend social values. Both intelligence and reasoning ability is powerful tool for problem solving behaviour (Chaube, 2005). It is essential for the development of any human being. So, it is necessary to identify the level of intelligence and reasoning ability of the students at the initial stage of education. At the initial stage of education (primary education), mathematics is an important subject in our curriculum. There is a strong relation among intelligence, mathematics and reasoning, because the main aim of mathematics is to develop different reasoning abilities and I.Q of students. The present study is a survey in nature to find out reasoning ability and intelligence among higher secondary students. The samples of the study consist of 100 students. Statistical techniques such as mean, Standard Deviation, t test and ‘r’ value were calculated to interpret the data. Reasoning ability test constructed and standardized by Ramellind Kynta was used. The findings of the study revealed that 12% of the student’s exhibit high Intelligence level, 60% student’s exhibit average and 28 % of the students exhibits low Intelligence level. Similarly, 31 % students showed low reasoning ability, 11% students showed high and, 58% students showed average level reasoning ability. Study also showed that there was a significant difference between boys and girls in terms of intelligence and reasoning ability. The study proved that there was a relationship between intelligence and reasoning ability.

Keywords: Intelligence, Ability, think, solves problems, analyse situations and comprehend social values Standard Deviation, Mathematics and Reasoning.

INTRODUCTION

Reasoning is a powerful tool for problem solving behaviour (Chaube, 2005). Reasoning and understanding skills are very important and essential for the development of any human being and

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its nation. So it is necessary to reason about reasoning and understanding at initial stage of education. At the initial stage of education (primary education), mathematics is an important subject in our curriculum. There is a strong relation between mathematics and reasoning, because the main aim of mathematics is to develop the logical reasoning power of human being. Due to researches in science and technology, physical labor is replaced by machines; knowledge of mathematics is in the root of such type of researches. Also knowledge of mathematics has become important in the development of technology, trades, information technology, medical science, space science, agriculture, optimization theory, network analysis, etc. Analytical part of several researches like social science and psychology are depending upon mathematics and logic. Mathematics is also called the science of logical reasoning. In it, we approach everything with a question mark in our mind. It is concluded that the reasoning power is concerned with development of all the sides of human life.

CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK

Different types of Reasoning

- Deductive Reasoning
- Inductive Reasoning
- Abductive Reasoning
- Backward Induction
- Critical thinking
- Counterfactual thinking
- Intuition

Scientific thinking

Scientific thinking can be generically defined as a set of cognitive processes and skills used to solve problems of a scientific nature, it can also be considered as the cognitive process that a researcher uses when performing studies or other typical scientific activities. Scientific thinking refers to the mental processes used when reasoning about the content of science engaged in typical scientific activities, or specific types of reasoning that are frequently used in science. Scientific thinking involves many general-purpose cognitive operations that human beings apply in non-scientific domains such as induction, deduction, analogy, problem solving, and causal reasoning. What distinguishes research on scientific thinking from general research on cognition

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is that research on scientific thinking typically involves investigating thinking that has scientific content. Among these cognitive functions we can mention induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, problem solving, causal reasoning or syllogistic reasoning, confrontation and implications, as well as fluency and flexibility of ideas or novelty and originality, which are more directly associated with creativity.

Critical Thinking and Intelligence

Critical thinking and intelligence are believed to go hand in hand. Unfortunately, that is one of the biggest misconceptions in regard to the subject. Intelligence refers to a person being extremely capable of solving difficult problems, just with maximum use of his/her brain.

Critical thinking, on the other hand, refers to people critically analysing a situation and arriving at a feasible solution, which may not necessarily be prompted by intelligence. So the two thought processes can differ in many ways and are not interdependent. An intelligent person might have lots of memories, data and information stored up, which he/she can immediately access in order to arrive at a solution. A critical thinker might not have such data readily available and will have to thoroughly analyse the situation and spend a little time in thinking of a solution. Both aspects can be critical in helping a person attain an applicable solution to the problem in question and it is just the process of getting there that might differ. Intelligence means the manner with which an individual deals with facts and situations. Intelligence is the aggregate or the global capacity of the individual to act purposefully, to think rationally and to deal effectively with the environment.

Deductive reasoning

Deductive reasoning is a formal method of top-down logic that seeks to find observations to prove a theory. It uses formal logic and produces logically certain results. Deductive reasoning is a basic form of valid reasoning. Deductive reasoning, or deduction, starts out with a general statement, or hypothesis, and examines the possibilities to reach a specific, logical conclusion. The scientific method uses deduction to test hypotheses and theories. "In deductive inference, we hold a theory and based on it we make a prediction of its consequences. That is, we predict what the observations should be if the theory were correct. We go from the general — the theory — to the specific — the observations. One of the most common types of deductive reasoning is a syllogism. Syllogism refers to two statements — a major and a minor statement — join to form a logical conclusion. The two accurate statements mean that the statement will likely be true for all additional premises of that

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category. One of the most common types of deductive reasoning is a syllogism. Syllogism refers to two statements — a major and a minor statement — join to form a logical conclusion. The two accurate statements mean that the statement will likely be true for all additional premises of that category.

Inductive reasoning

Inductive reasoning is a bottom-up logic that seeks theories to explain observations. It is exploratory in nature, and allows for uncertain but likely results. Inductive reasoning is the opposite of deductive reasoning. Inductive reasoning makes broad generalizations from specific observations. Basically, there is data, then conclusions are drawn from the data. This is called inductive logic. In inductive inference, we go from the specific to the general. We make many observations, discern a pattern, make a generalization, and infer an explanation or a theory. In science, there is a constant interplay between inductive inference (based on observations) and deductive inference (based on theory), until we get closer and closer to the 'truth,' which we can only approach but not ascertain with complete certainty. Inductive reasoning is the opposite of deductive reasoning. In this process, you would gather generalized information from specific scenarios to come to a conclusion, rather than taking specific assumptions from generalized scenarios. Inductive reasoning is often used to create a hypothesis rather than apply them to different scenarios. With inductive reasoning, the accuracy of the outcome is probable, but not always true, even if each of the first two statements is accurate.

Abductive reasoning

Like Induction, Abductive reasoning seeks theories to explain observations. It is less rigorous and allow for best guesses. Abductive reasoning is typically used in the context of uncertainty. It is associated with decision making and trouble shooting. It is another form of scientific reasoning that doesn't fit in with inductive or deductive reasoning is abductive. Abductive reasoning usually starts with an incomplete set of observations and proceeds to the likeliest possible explanation for the group of observations. It is based on making and testing hypotheses using the best information available. It often entails making an educated guess after observing a phenomenon for which there is no clear explanation.

Abductive reasoning uses all the available information, even if it's incomplete, to determine the most likely outcome or an educated guess. While it uses the best information currently available, it's usually not enough to make a fully informed, certain conclusion. With abductive reasoning, it is also possible

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that the conclusion cannot be tested. Abduction is often associated with the kind of reasoning used in the construction of hypotheses in the discovery stage of scientific evidence. Abduction as a process where we find some very curious circumstance, which would be explained by the supposition that it was a case of a certain general rule, and there upon adopt that supposition. Abduction is based on explanation of a given fact or finding, a "curious circumstance. The words "supposition" and "adopt" suggest the tentative nature of abduction. We can accept an abductively derived conclusion as a provisional commitment even if it is subject to retraction in the future. The expression "general rule" is significant. Abductive inferences are derived from the way things can normally be expected to go in a familiar kind of situation, or as a "general rule." A general rule may not hold in all cases of a certain kind. It is not based on a warrant of "for all x ," as deductive inferences so often are. It is not even based on a finding of most or countable many cases, as inductive inferences so often are. It holds only for normal or familiar cases and may fall outside this range of "general rule" cases.

Backward induction

Backward induction is the process of reasoning **backwards** in time, from the end of a problem or situation, to determine a sequence of optimal actions. It proceeds by first considering the last time a decision might be made and choosing what to do in any situation at that time. Backward induction is a top-down approach that starts with theories or end-states and work backwards to explains them, It allows for uncertainty and is commonly used in artificial intelligence. For example, it is a classic way for a computer to play chess by considering game end-states and working backwards to evaluate moves. Backward induction in game theory is an iterative process of reasoning **backward** in time, from the end of a problem or situation, to solve finite extensive form and sequential games, and infer a sequence of optimal actions Backwards induction: start with base case $n = N$ and go **backwards**, instead of starting at base case $n = 1$ and going forwards. Two-step **induction**, where the proof for $n = x + 1$ relies not only on the formula being true for $n = x$, but also on it being true for $n = x - 1$.

Intuition

Intuitions are judgements that are made by the mind that are perceived by the unconscious. Such judgements exhibit intelligence but the processes by which they are generated are not well understood. Although intuition is sometimes taken lightly, it has played a significant role in

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scientific discovery. Intuition is the apparent ability of the human mind to acquire knowledge without conscious thought. In brain's method of arriving at intuitive information is unknown to the thinker. Intuition is not well understanding something of a mystery.

Counterfactual thinking

Counterfactual thinking is considering things that known to be impossible..The most common example of this is evaluating the past decisions that were once possible but are now impossible as their time horizon has passed. Considering here past decisions might have worked out is common human thought process that may improve decision making abilities. Counterfactual thinking is a common type of thought pattern that goes back in time to evaluate choices weren't made. It is typified by questions like "what if I had ..."As a time horizon passes, choices that were once available may become impossible. Counterfactual think of examining the impossible to extract insights that can be applied elsewhere. In other words, evaluating can have value in improving future decision making or solving a problem.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Reasoning (inductive and deductive) is generally considered as the hallmark indicator of Giftedness. How reasoning tasks are conceptualized and measured may influence their predictive power of academic performance (Lohman & Lakin, 2011). Specifically, task modality and task complexity of reasoning tasks are two major factors that may influence the relations between reasoning tasks and academic performance. Based on the intrinsic cognitive load theory, the composite nonverbal reasoning is more likely to sample various reasoning skills and thus is assumed to have stronger relations with academic achievement than a specific nonverbal reasoning measure.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The title of the present study was as under,

“A study of reasoning ability of secondary school students in relation to their intelligence”.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF THE KEY TERMS

Reasoning

According to Dictionary of Oxford Advanced Learner (6th ed., 2003),“Reasoning: The process of thinking about things in a logical way; opinions and ideas that are based on logical

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thinking.”According to **Aristotle**, (As cited in Microsoft Encarta Encyclopedia,2004), Reason: Ability to think logically and analytically. According to **Skinner** (1968), Reasoning is the word used to describe the mental recognition of cause and effect relationship.

It may be prediction of an event from an observed cause or the inference of a cause from an observed event. According to **Gates** (1947), Reasoning is a productive thinking in which previous experiences are organized in new way to solve problem. In the present study, Reasoning is a mental process in which one uses the past experiences of mathematics to solve a new problem.

Ability

According to Dictionary of Oxford Advanced Learner (6th ed., 2003), “A level of skill or intelligence, the fact that somebody/something is able to do something.” According to Encyclopedia of Education (2010), “The capability to perform an act, either innate or as the result of learning and practice.” In the present study, ability means ability or capacity to solve a new problem by using reasoning.

Reasoning Ability

Reasoning is defined as a process of thinking that evaluates a situation in a logical manner to come to a conclusion. Reasoning ability depends on various parameters like experience, critical thinking abilities and emotions.

Intelligence

In ancient India our great rishis and seers named it Viveka. Intelligence is difficult to define. Theoretically it is the capacity to learn new information, to understand one’s world and to be resourceful in coping with challenges. Intelligence consists of abilities necessary to adapt to the environment to achieve goals. An intelligent person can understand what is going on around and, can also learn from experience and then can act in ways that are successful in the environment. Intelligence is a person’s ability to adapt to the environment in all aspects of his or her life, a difficult concept to measure. Jean Piaget (1952): Intelligence is the ability to adapt to one’s surrounding. For instance they define intelligence as the ability to learn, to deal with abstractions, to make adjustments, to adapt to new situations, or the ability or power to make appropriate responses to certain stimuli in a given situation. Intelligence is the aggregate or global capacity of an individual to act purposefully, to think rationally, and to deal effectively with his environment.

Secondary

A secondary school describes an institution that provides secondary education and also usually includes the building where this takes place. Secondary schools follow on from primary schools and prepare for vocational or tertiary education. Attendance is usually compulsory for students until age 16.

VARIABLES

Variables used for study are

- i) Reasoning ability
- ii) Intelligence

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the status of individual student on Intelligence of standard 9th.
2. To study the intelligence of 9th standard students based on gender.
3. To study the status of individual student on Reasoning ability of standard 9th.
4. To study the reasoning ability of 9th standard students based on gender.
5. To study the relationship between the Reasoning ability and Intelligence of secondary school students.

HYPOTH ESES

Ho1: There is no significance relationship between the intelligence of secondary school students based on gender.

Ho2: There is no significance relationship between the reasoning ability of secondary school students based on gender.

Ho3: There is no significance relationship between the reasoning ability of secondary school students and their intelligence.

METHODOLOGY

The investigator selected reasoning ability test constructed by Ramellind Kynta. Inductive reasoning, Deductive reasoning, Analogical reasoning, Eclectic reasoning and classification as reasoning were included. The test comprises of subtests viz - Rearranging words, Rearranging sentences. Relationship, odd word, opposites, number series and complete the word test. The draft

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of the test containing 100 items was prepared covering five different sub-tests. Necessary instruction and direction were worked for all the five sub-tests. A separate response sheet and scoring key were also prepared. Following this, the test was carried out on a sample of 100 Class 9th students of St. Michael’s Girls HSS, west hill, and St. Joseph’s Boys HSS in Kozhikode District. The test was done in order to

- (i) Obtain objective information of each and every item
- (ii) Arrange the selected items in ascending order of difficulty and
- (iii) Fix up the time limit for each sub-test.

The pupils were given enough time to complete the test. They were clearly instructed how to attempt the items for all the five subtests and also to note down the time taken after completing each sub-test.

SAMPLES

- a. The researcher intended to find out the relation between reasoning ability and intelligence. For this purpose, he selected St. Michael’s Girls HSS, west hill and St. Joseph’s Boys HSS in Kozhikode District.

The students of class 9th were selected as a sample of the investigation.

- b. Area: Urban
- c. Number of schools: two
- d. Number of students: 100
- e. Gender: Girls and Boys
- f. Strata: 2 (Girls and Boys)
- g. Type of schools: Government aided.
- h. Medium: Malayalam

TOOLS FOR THE STUDY

Reasoning ability test constructed and standardized by Ramellind Kynta.

STATISTICAL TECHNICAL USED

Suitable descriptive and inferential statistic techniques are intended to use in the interpretation of the data to draw out meaningful picture from the collected data. In the present study the following statistical measures are intended to use.

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MEAN

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\sum fd}{N}$$

Where,

f = Frequency of the class interval

A = Assumed mean

N = Sum of the frequencies

I = Width of the class interval

d = X-A/I (Deviation from the assumed mean)

SPEARMAN RANK COEFFICIENT OF CORRELATION

$$r = 1 - \frac{6 \sum D^2}{N(N^2 - 1)}$$

$N(N^2 - 1)$

D = the difference between paired ranks

D² = the sum of the squared differences between ranks

N = number of paired ranks

STANDARD DEVIATION

$$\sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{N} - \left(\frac{\sum fd}{N}\right)^2}$$

Where,

f = Frequency of the class

d = X-A/I (Deviation from the assumed mean)

N = Sum of the frequencies

i = Width of the class interval

‘t’ TEST

$$t = \frac{M_1 - M_2}{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{N_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{N_2}}}$$

Where,

M₁ - M₂ = Difference between means M₁ and M₂.

σ₁, σ₂ = Standard deviations

N₁, N₂ = Total number of each group.

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LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE

In the present study the investigator would like to test all hypotheses for acceptance or rejection at 0.05 level of significance. The result obtained through the statistical analysis of data will be compared with the value for 0.05 level of significance to retain or reject the hypothesis formulated by the investigator for the present study.

ANALYSIS OF OBJECTIVES

Analysis of objective 1:

To study the status of individual student on Intelligence of standard 9th

Level	Number of students	Percentage
High	12	12%
Average	60	60%
Low	28	28%

High : 64.8 and above

Average : 45.3 -- 64.7

Low : 45.2 and below

Table Analysis: From the above table, 12% students are high on Intelligence level, 60% students are average on Intelligence level and 28 % are low on Intelligence level.

Analysis of objective 2:

To study the intelligence of 9th standard students based on gender

Table showing Mean, S.D., and ‘t’ value of the Intelligence of 9th std students based on gender

variable	category	N	mean	SD	‘t’
Intelligence	Male	50	52	9.18	3.04
	Female	50	58	10.45	

Table Analysis: From the above table, the calculated ‘t’ value (3.04) is greater than the table value (1.96) significance at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis is rejected and the research hypothesis is accepted.

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Analysis of objective 3:

To study the status of individual student on reasoning ability of standard 9th

Level	Number of students	Percentage
High	11	11%
Average	58	58%
Low	31	31%

High : 23.13 and above

Average : 10.68 -- 23.12

Low : 10.67 and below

Table Analysis: From the above table, 11% students are high on Intelligence level, 58% students are average on Intelligence level and 31 % are low on Intelligence level.

Analysis of objective 4:

To study the Reasoning ability of 9th standard students based on gender.

Table showing Mean, S.D., and ‘t’ value of the Reasoning ability of 9th std students based on gender.

Variable	Category	N	Mean	SD	‘t’
Reasoning Ability	Male	50	15.3	7.503	2.6
	Female	50	18.57	4.956	

Table Analysis: From the above table, the calculated ‘t’ value (2.6) is greater than the table value (1.96) significance at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis is rejected and the research hypothesis is accepted.

Analysis of objective 5:

To study the relationship between the reasoning ability and intelligence of secondary school students.

Table showing Mean, S.D., Rank Correlation Coefficient ‘r’ and ‘t’ value of the 9th standard students based on Intelligence and Reasoning ability.

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Variable	N	Mean	SD	r	‘t’	Level of significance
Reasoning Ability	50	62.4	6.1	0.54	6.52	Significant at 0.05 level
Intelligence	50	56.4	7.31			

Table Analysis: From the above table, the calculated ‘t’ value (6.52) is greater than the table value (1.96) significance at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis is rejected and the research hypothesis is accepted.

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- ❖ The status of individual student on Intelligence is Average.
- ❖ There is significant difference between the intelligence of 9th standard students based on gender.
- ❖ The status of individual student on Reasoning ability is Average.
- ❖ There is significant difference between the Reasoning ability of 9th standard students based on gender.
- ❖ There is relationship between the Reasoning ability and the Intelligence of secondary school students.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The sample was limited. The same study can be conducted with large number of samples.
- The present study was restricted to secondary school students.
- The study was conducted in very small area.

CONCLUSION

The present study aimed at analyzing the reasoning ability of secondary school students in relation to their intelligence, with special variables like reasoning ability and intelligence. The study indicates that there is significant differences and relationship between the variables.
